

fertilizer was 40 kg N (urea), 17.6 kg P (superphosphate), 33 kg K (potassium chloride), and 3,000 kg CaO (calcium carbonate)/ ha .

Forty-day-old seedlings were planted at 20×20cm spacing in a randomized

complete block design. Plants were scored for Fe toxicity on a 1-9 scale at 4 and 8 wk after transplanting. Grain yield was recorded at maturity.

Varietal differences in tolerance for Fe toxicity were noticed. Fe toxicity was

more severe at 4 wk than at 8 wk after transplanting (Table 2). Addition of P and Ca fertilizers reduced its extent. Local variety Guichao yielded significantly more than any of the test varieties. *ℳ*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Experimental mutagenic method for improving rice strains in Vietnam

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The National Strain Testing Centre (NSTC) of Vietnam has tested two rice mutants. Mutant DB250 is the result of irradiating F₁ dry grains from the cross of TB₁ (a Vietnamese local variety) and IR22 at 25 kR along with 0.02% N-Nitrozo N-dimethylurea as spray for 6 h.

DB250 is 1.35-1.50 m high, has a hard and big culm, is adapted to deep water, and responds to 120 kg N/ha. It was

submerged 7-10 d after 4 wk of culture, but mortality was not high. At maximum tillering, submergence for 12 d resulted in 20% mortality, compared with 80% for IR27 and several IRRI strains. DB250 has a 1000-grain weight of 26-27 g and yields 4.5 t/ha over a large area. In NST-C tests in 1980-83 in 14 provinces of the North, DB250 was first among 16 adapted submergence-tolerant rices.

Mutant NN22-98 was obtained in 1973 by treating IR22 grains with 0.02% N-NitroLoethylurea for 18 h (pH 7). It was separated from the M₂ population in 1974.

NN22-98 is 1.2-1.4 m high, has a hard culm, is adapted to deep water, and responds to as much as 100 kg N/ha. Its 1,000-grain weight is 29-31 g, compared with the normal 23-25 g. The plant has field resistance to brown planthopper biotypes 1 and 2. Mean yield is 4.4-4.6 t/ha. Grain quality is better than that of IR22.

NN22-98 was third among 16 strains of summer rice tested by the NSTC in 1980-83 in 19 provinces of the North. It is still being tested by the Ministry of Agriculture. *ℳ*

Comparison of rice hybrids and local varieties at TNRRRI

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Seven rice hybrids from IRRI were tested against three short-duration and five medium-duration Tamil Nadu varieties during 1984 kharif. The trial was laid out in a randomized block with three replications. The 24-d-old seedlings were planted, 1 seedling/hill spaced 20 cm between rows and 15 cm within rows, in 10.35 m² plots and fertilized 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha. No plant protection measures were taken, as there was no pest or disease incidence during growth.

Among the hybrids studied, Wei You 64 flowered very early (72 d after seeding [DAS]); IR21895-90-3A/IR54 and IR46830A/IR13292-5-2 flowered late (106 DAS). The remaining hybrids

Performance of rice hybrids and local varieties. TNRRRI, Aduthurai, India.

Hybrid and variety	Days to 50% flowering	Height (cm)	Yield (t/ha)
Wei You 64	72	89.6	4.5
IR46831A/IR54	87	87.5	4.2
IR41828A/Milyang 54	77	81.9	3.7
IR365A/Milyang 54	87	93.7	3.5
97A/Milyang 54	78	97.3	3.1
IR21895-90-3A/IR54	106	123.3	4.0
IR46830A/IR13292-5-2	106	89.4	4.2
IR50 (IR2153-14-1-6-2/IR28//IR36)	76	85.3	4.1
TKM9 (TKM7/IR8)	77	94.9	4.0
ADT36 (Tiruveni/IR20)	79	94.3	4.0
Co 42 (RP-31-49-2/Lab Muey Mahag)	102	124.0	4.2
IR20 (Peta*3/TN1//TKM6)	103	104.4	3.9
Co 44 (ASD5/IR20)	99	104.4	4.1
Co 43 (Dasal/IR20)	99	101.4	4.0
White Ponni (AD)	101	152.8	3.9
CD			3.8
CV			9.5

flowered between 77 and 87 DAS (see table).

IR21895-90-3A/IR54 was tallest of the hybrids, and lodged. White Ponni (AD), one of the medium-duration tall check varieties, also lodged. Check Co

42 partly lodged.

Although yield differences among the hybrids and the check varieties were significant, the yield potential of the hybrids was less than 4.5 t/ha. The maximum yield (4.5 t/ha) was registered